

Sensitivity of acetylcholinesterases of susceptible (S) and MIPC-resistant (R) *N. lugens* strains to carbamate insecticides, Taiwan.

Insecticide	RR ^a	<i>N. lugens</i> strains		
		S	R	Ratio
MIPC	41	0.23	3.62	15.7
MTMC	80	5.86	18.0	3.1
Propoxur	76	0.15	1.10	7.3
Carbofuran	73	0.08	0.33	4.1
Carbaryl	41	0.38	0.92	2.4
Methomyl	33	6.99	29.4	4.2

^aResistance ratio = LC₅₀ of R strain divided by LC₅₀ of S strain.

less inhibited by several other carbamate insecticides.

A decrease of AChE sensitivity might be the primary cause of MIPC resistance in brown planthopper. A secondary cause is degradation of MIPC mediated by esterases, since a DEF inhibitor of these enzymes enhances the toxicity of MIPC to R strain. Insensitivity of AChE also contributed to brown planthopper resistance to several other carbamates. ■

Pest management and control WEEDS

Integrated weed management in dry-land rice

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Weeds are a serious problem for direct-sown, short-duration, high-yielding rice-cultivars in Eastern India. This study involved 2 methods of sowing (broadcast and row), 3 seed rates (70, 90, and 110 kg/ha), 4 weed control treatments (nitrofen thiobencarb, propanil, and manual), and unweeded and untreated controls. The experiment was laid out in

a split-plot design with method of sowing and seed rate as the main plots and weed control and unweeded treatment as subplots.

Irrespective of seed rates, sowing in rows recorded higher plant populations, lower dry matter accumulation in weeds, and higher grain yield than broadcast method of sowing (see table). High seed rates recorded higher plant populations, lower dry matter accumulation of weeds, and higher grain yields than low seed rates.

Thiobencarb as a preemergence herbicide was slightly phytotoxic to rice, caus-

ing mortality of some seedlings. Maximum grain yield was obtained with propanil applied as split doses of 1.5 kg a.i./ha each at 15 and 30 days after sowing (DS) or high seed rate sown in rows. Manual weed control by hoeing once 15 DS and hand weeding 30 DS was next in yield. Propanil treatment reduced the dry matter accumulation in weeds from 324.7 g/m² to 68.8 g/m². Nutrient loss of 19.3 kg N/ha, 11.6 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 68.1 kg K₂O/ha in the unweeded control was reduced to 3.1 kg N/ha, 2.5 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 14.5 kg K₂O/ha with propanil. ■

Effects of sowing method, seed rate, and weed control treatment in Orissa, India.^a

Treatment	Plant population (no./m ²) 10 DS	Dry matter accumulation of weeds (g/m ²) 60 DS	Nutrient uptake by weeds (kg/ha) 60 DS			Grain yield (t/ha)
			N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	
Sowing method						
Broadcasting	107.5	171.0	10.5	6.3	33.7	1.5
Row	143.5	156.8	9.0	5.4	25.9	1.8
Seed rate (kg/ha)						
70	115.6	151.8	9.6	5.6	33.1	1.6
90	128.4	142.6	8.1	4.9	30.8	1.4
110	146.4	104.1	6.1	4.9	23.9	2.0
Weed control method						
Nitrofen@ 1.5 kg a.i./ha 2 DS	150.7	151.5	9.0	5.4	31.9	1.6
Thiobencarb @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha 2 DS	112.0	166.6	10.7	7.0	41.4	1.2
Propanil @ 1.5 kg a.i./ha each 15 and 30 DS	158.0	68.8	3.1	2.5	14.5	2.8
Manual	146.3	76.9	4.6	2.8	16.4	2.1
Unweeded control	155.5	324.7	19.3	11.6	68.1	0.6
CD (0.05) for sowing method	20.6	7.3				0.04
CD (0.05) for seed rate	25.2	9.6				0.05
CD (0.05) for weed control method	11.2	16.4				0.09

^aDS = days after sowing.

Effects of herbicides and water management regimes on weeds and grain yields of transplanted rice in India

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The use of several herbicides under different water management treatments was tried in a replicated field trial at the Agriculture Research Station, Bhubaneswar, during the 1977 and 1978 wet seasons.

Continuous submergence had significantly the lowest weed population and weed weight (see table). Fluchloralin treatment showed promising effects on weed control at all the levels of water

Treatment	1977 crop season			1978 crop Season		
	Weed population (no./m ²)	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weed population (no./m ²)	Dry wt of weeds (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
	40 DT	at harvest		40 DT	at harvest	
<i>Main plot</i>						
Continuous 10 cm submergence to grain filling	67.6	18.5	3.5	59.3	15.8	3.3
Saturation to maturity and 5 cm submergence to dough stage	88.5	21.8	3.1	62.8	16.6	3.3
Saturation to grain filling	114.6	29.1	2.6	87.9	22.8	3.0
<i>Subplot^a</i>						
Fluchloralin EC @ 0.8 kg a.i./ha	23.3	12.6	3.4	38.1	9.4	3.3
2,4-D EE (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	30.8	14.2	3.3	40.5	11.2	3.3
Butachlor (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	46.1	14.8	3.2	56.7	10.4	3.1
Thiobencarb (G) @ 1.0 kg a.i./ha	52.8	15.9	3.1	39.5	9.2	3.3
Manual weeding at 25 and 50 days after planting	37.1	13.0	3.3	39.3	9.8	3.3
Unweeded control	233.7	70.4	2.5	156.8	58.4	2.7
CD (0.05) for water management practice	4.9	3.0	0.3	1.4	1.4	0.2
CD (0.05) for herbicides	8.4	2.7	0.5	4.3	1.3	0.3

^a Fluchloralin was applied as preplanting soil spray a day before transplanting; granular formulations of 2,4-D EE, butachlor, and thiobencarb were applied directly 7 days after transplanting (DT).

management.

Continuous submergence from 7 days

after planting to harvest recorded the highest grain yields. Preplanting treat-

ment with fluchloralin recorded the maximum grain yield. ■

Pest management and control OTHER PESTS

Efficacy of brodifacoum baits against rodents in storage areas

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Brodifacoum is a new anticoagulant rodenticide of exceptional activity against rodent species both resistant and susceptible to other conventional rodenticides. The formulated product, which contains 50 ppm active ingredient (a.i.), is highly toxic and can provide a single-feeding action for many species. It compares with Warfarin baits containing 250 ppm a.i. in its adverse effect to man and domestic animals. Accidental poisoning can be countered with treatments of Vitamin K₁.

Baiting tests at the short-term storage room and seed processing lab of the International Rice Research Institute showed that brodifacoum pellet baits were effective in controlling mice infestations.

During the 26-day baiting period, high bait intake was followed by decline

1. Daily consumption of brodifacoum bait at the Rice Genetic Resources Laboratory storage room, IRRRI, 1980.

and death of mice (Fig. 1). That indicated migrants or even new-generation mice from births in the original population just before control.

A long-term baiting trial indicated that mice population was kept at satisfactorily low levels by maintaining adequate baiting points. Better control was